

IMPACT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of corporate governance (audit committee composition, ownership concentration, managerial ownership) on the financial performance (earnings per share) of listed DMBs in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Secondary data were sourced from the individual financial reports of the listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The sample adopted 13 listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. This study employed a regression model to estimate the relationship between corporate governance and the financial performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria. The results revealed that audit committee composition and managerial ownership exert significant positive effects on the performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria. Ownership concentration had an insignificant effect on the firm performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria. The study recommended that DMBs should ensure that audit committees comprise independent, skilled, and adequately trained members. Emphasis should be placed on enhancing oversight functions, risk management, and compliance to improve transparency and profitability. Furthermore, DMBs should consider mechanisms that allow managers to hold meaningful equity stakes, thereby aligning their interests with those of shareholders. Such alignment can enhance decision-making, accountability, and performance. Finally, CBN should continue monitoring large shareholder influence to ensure that dominant investors do not engage in practices that undermine the interests or operational efficiency of minority shareholders.

Introduction

Globally, financial performance is a key determinant of a company's success and competitive edge. It is frequently deemed the most reliable measure of an organization's profitability, stability, and efficiency, offering valuable insights into management effectiveness and operational integrity (Altania & Tanno, 2023). High financial performance not only draws in investors and enhances shareholder trust but also empowers companies to obtain

capital, grow operations, and preserve a lasting competitive advantage. This is especially crucial in the African context, where economic challenges and market fluctuations are prevalent, making financial performance essential for sustaining a firm's market relevance and ensuring its long-term viability. Businesses must maintain strong financial health to endure competitive challenges and fulfill stakeholder expectations (Shan et al., 2023). Corporate governance is a framework designed to manage and regulate to enhance shareholder value and fulfill stakeholder expectations. In Nigeria, the initial effort to establish a corporate governance code for public companies occurred in 2003 when the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) released the Code of Corporate Governance for Public Companies, intended to complement the existing legal framework of corporate governance principles, especially the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA), the Investment and Securities Act (ISA), and other statutory regulations. Nonetheless, the shortcomings that emerged during the execution of the SEC 2003 Code of Corporate Governance (CG) prompted the introduction of a new code, which took effect on April 1, 2011. The 2011 Code applies to all public companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and those aiming to raise capital from the Nigerian market. The primary goal of the Code of Corporate Governance for Public Companies 2011 is to encourage sound corporate governance practices among public companies in Nigeria and align the Code with international best practices (Olayiwola, 2018). Thus, corporate governance is measured using audit committee composition, ownership concentration, and managerial ownership.

The composition of the audit committee is a key corporate governance mechanism that influences the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, particularly their EPS. An effective audit committee, composed of independent, financially literate, and experienced members, strengthens financial reporting, internal controls, and risk management oversight. This improves transparency, reduces the likelihood of earnings manipulation, and fosters investor confidence, which can translate into higher profitability (Sarea, 2020). Consequently, managerial ownership may have a significant relationship with financial performance. When managers own shares, their interests are more closely aligned with those of shareholders, reducing agency conflicts. This alignment motivates managers to pursue strategies that enhance profitability, minimize wasteful expenditures, and carefully manage risks, thereby potentially increasing EPS (Areneke et al., 2022).

Despite the introduction of several reforms and regulatory codes by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), banks have continued to collapse, with persistent concerns about the extent to which corporate governance structures truly influence the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The persistence of banking failures, loss of shareholder value, and increasing cases of unethical practices point to a fundamental research problem (dissolution of boards at Union Bank, Keystone Bank, and Polaris Bank indicate regulatory action for non-compliance): to what extent does corporate governance explain Nigerian deposit money banks' financial performance? However, the main objective of this study is to examine the impact of corporate governance on the financial performance of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks from 2014 to 2023. Based on the problem statement and the study objectives, the following hypotheses are described in a null form to guide the study:

- i. Composition of the audit committee has no significant impact on earnings per share of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria
- ii. Ownership concentration does not have a significant impact on the earnings per share of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks.
- iii. Managerial ownership has no significant impact on the earnings per share of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks.

Literature Review

The concept of financial performance

Financial performance is a subjective indicator of how effectively a company can leverage its core business assets to generate revenue. This term is also used as a broad measure of a company's overall financial well-being over a specific time frame and can be used to compare similar companies within the same industry or to collectively assess entire sectors or industries. Yarram et al. (2020) defined it as the achievement of pre-established objectives, targets, and goals within a designated time frame. Several factors, including the time period and reference point, must be considered when trying to define performance. It is possible to distinguish between historical and future performance. Research indicates that past excellent performance does not ensure continued superiority in the future (Santos & Brito, 2012). Nevertheless, this study will assess financial performance through the market value ratio, represented by earnings per share (EPS), as companies currently prioritize maximizing shareholder wealth over merely maximizing profits.

Corporate Governance Concept

Corporate governance revolves around managing the relationships among the board of directors, shareholders, employees, and regulators, both internal and external to the company, ensuring proper interactions among these groups in overseeing the company's activities. Corporate governance primarily arises from the commitment to tackle the challenge of separating ownership from management (Eneh, 2018). Mueller (2006) identifies two categories of corporate governance institutions: those that are ubiquitous across all companies in a nation, such as legal frameworks and institutions, and those that vary between companies within a nation, such as the size of the board of directors or the proportion of independent members on the board. According to Tricker (2015), corporate governance can be divided into four domains of authority: ownership authority, corporate directors' authority, management authority, and institutional authority. Luo (2005) stated that corporate governance operates through three mechanisms: market-based mechanisms (including board composition, board size, market discipline, chairmanship of the board, executive pay, and interconnected directorates); culture-based mechanisms (which encompass governance culture and corporate integrity); and discipline-based mechanisms (such as executive penalties, internal auditing, codes of conduct, and ethics programs).

Composition of the Audit Committee

The audit committee composition is set up as part of the corporate governance monitoring and control mechanism in the company's finance and accounting activities. The audit committee periodically reviews the organization's financial reports, which are made available to the board of directors and shareholders, as well as to regulatory bodies (Angsoyiri, 2021). Audit composition is defined as the probability that the external auditor will detect and report any client accounting system violations (Amahalu & Obi, 2020).

Ownership Concentration

Ownership concentration is a significant internal governance mechanism in which owners can control and influence the firm's management to protect their interests. This research focuses on the relationship between ownership concentration and firms' corporate governance and disclosure practices. Ownership concentration refers to the extent to which a firm's equity is held by some shareholders. It reflects the distribution of control and decision-making power in a corporation (Areneke et al., 2022). According to agency theory, ownership concentration can influence the degree of monitoring exerted on managers, thereby affecting firm performance and governance outcomes.

Managerial Ownership

Managerial ownership is represented as the proportion of shares owned by insiders and board members or insider ownership. Olayinka (2021) defined managerial ownership as the percentage of executive directors holding shares. He also viewed managerial ownership as the proportion of executives' shares. Olayinka (2021) also defined managerial ownership as a situation in which insiders or managers act as shareholders if they acquire a considerable proportion of an entity's shares. The relationship between managerial ownership and dividend policy Jensen (1986) argued that managers prefer to retain earnings rather than give it to shareholders as a dividend. Managers want to use the resources for the firm's growth as well as for personal benefits. Oyedokun et al. (2020) opined that insiders or managers of a firm also act as shareholders if they possess some portion of the company shares. This reduces agency conflicts and aligns the interests of management and shareholders. Managerial ownership signifies managers' interest in a firm's equity shareholding.

Empirical Review

Sudyantara et al. (2025) analyzed the effect of managerial ownership on MSMEs' financial performance in Pacitan, especially in terms of increasing profitability. Using a quantitative approach, data from 113 MSMEs were analyzed using the simple linear regression method. The results showed that managerial ownership has a significant influence on financial performance, with a value of $R=0.645$ and $R^2=41.6\%$. This means that approximately 41.6% of the variation in the financial performance of MSMEs is explained by the level of managerial ownership. This finding implies that managers who also own shares tend to make strategic decisions that increase efficiency and profitability. However, 58.4% of the variation in the financial performance of MSMEs is influenced by other factors, such as access to capital, operational efficiency, and managerial capability. In the context of MSMEs in Pacitan, these results provide an important foundation for designing more effective management strategies. The findings have practical implications for local governments, financial institutions, and MSME players in optimizing ownership structures to improve competitiveness. By understanding the role of managerial ownership, MSMEs are expected to be more competitive in local and regional markets. This research highlights the importance of an integrated approach in MSMEs management to support business growth and sustainability.

Nazhila and Amin (2024) determined the influence of independent commissioners on the managerial ownership of green accounting on the financial performance of companies in the non-cyclical consumer sector. The data sources used are primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained from questionnaires. Secondary data from company data, journals, and books. Independent commissioners positively impact financial performance. Companies can enhance financial performance through objective and independent oversight through more effective management, increased transparency, and greater investor confidence. Managerial ownership significantly improves financial performance. Management has a strong incentive to encourage financial performance, minimize conflicts of interest, and make more strategic decisions when it holds company shares. Similarly, green accounting has a notable positive effect on financial performance.

Altania and Tanno (2023) investigated the effect of managerial and institutional ownership on a company's financial performance. The method used in this research is a quantitative approach. This study uses a secondary research approach with research objects in the form of manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the 2017-2021 period. The results of this study indicate that managerial ownership significantly influences a company's financial performance. This is supported by a significance value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Managerial ownership can have a significant positive impact on a company's financial performance because it can increase management's motivation to work harder and pay more attention to the company's long-

term performance. In addition, the results of this study also show that institutional ownership significantly influences the company's financial performance, indicated by a significance value of 0.025, which is less than 0.05. Institutional ownership can increase company management oversight, provide positive signals to the market, and help companies obtain greater resources.

Shan et al. (2023) used evidence from the Chinese stock market to investigate the relationship between managerial ownership and financial distress. It also analyzes whether the relationship is mediated by R&D investment. This study employs both piecewise and curvilinear models using a dataset consisting of 19,059 firm-year observations of Chinese listed companies in the Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges between 2010 and 2020. The results indicate that managerial ownership is negatively associated with firm financial distress in both the low (below 12%) and high (above 18%) convergence-of-interest regions of managerial ownership, suggesting that managerial ownership in this region may contribute to improving firm financial status. Meanwhile, managerial ownership is positively associated with firm financial distress in the entrenchment region (12–18%), implying that managerial ownership in the entrenchment region may impair firm financial status. Furthermore, R&D investment mediates the association between managerial ownership and financial distress. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to provide evidence of a nonlinear relationship between managerial ownership and financial distress and to identify the entrenchment region in the Chinese context.

Sharma et al. (2022) examined the effect of corporate governance-related determinants and firms' (non-) financial consequences of CSR. Legitimacy theory, as our theoretical framework, assumes that a company must fulfill the respective society's values and expectations and gain legitimacy through a social contract. We also rely on the business case argument, assuming a positive relationship between the firm's CSR and financial outcomes. This analysis focuses on 54 quantitative meta-analyses on CSR and includes a structured literature review to increase our knowledge of which corporate governance variables and proxies of a firm's (non) financial outcome have been heavily included in archival research and if these variables have an overall impact. Prior meta-analyses indicate that board independence, board gender diversity, and board size have a positive impact on CSR performance. Moreover, both CSR and environmental performance increase financial performance. This literature review makes a useful contribution to prior studies by summarizing the overall impact of CGI variables on CSR and their (non-) financial consequences and deducing recommendations for future research.

Altin (2024) investigated the impact of the characteristics of audit committees on firm performance. In particular, the authors employ the random-effects variant of the Hunter–Schmidt meta-analysis procedure to analyze the effects of key audit committee attributes, namely, audit committee independence, audit committee expertise, audit committee size, and audit committee meeting, along with the Big Four impact on firm performance. The authors hope to gain a better understanding of the function of audit committees in enhancing firm performance and uncover potential discrepancies in prior findings due to varying economic levels or performance metrics. This study uses the Hunter–Schmidt method to conduct a meta-analysis of 39 studies published between 2012 and 2022 to investigate the relationship between the characteristics of audit committees and firm performance. The results indicate that audit committee independence, expertise, size, and affiliation with the Big Four have a significant and positive effect on firm performance, whereas audit committee meetings have a non-significant effect. Furthermore, the findings indicate that when designing and implementing governance mechanisms, companies should carefully consider the contextual factors that may impact the effectiveness of their corporate governance structures, such as economic level. This study is significant as it is the first to combine and analyze previous research on this topic and highlights the importance of certain audit committee characteristics in enhancing FRQ and CG.

Krishnamoorthy et al. (2022) examined the effect of the financial expertise (AFE) residing in the AC chair on the monitoring of financial reporting quality and the audit process. Based on a sample of over 13,840 observations from U.S. public companies, we find that the AFE of the AC chair is associated with lower levels of earnings management and enhanced audit process monitoring. When augmented by AC members with AFE, AFE is also negatively associated with reduced misstatement risk. This finding suggests that appointing an AFE to the AC may not in itself be sufficient to fully enhance oversight quality, unless the committee also has an AFE. Finally, chair AFE is also found to enhance the likelihood of reporting material control weaknesses and goodwill impairments.

Lutfi et al. (2022) examined the extent to which the characteristics of the audit committee chair enhance the quality of financial reports and reduce the possibility of receiving a modified audit opinion (MAO) from an external auditor. We apply logistic regression to investigate the influence of ACC characteristics on the FRQ (FRQ) for a sample of 460 firm-year observations (service and industrial companies listed) on the Amman Stock Exchange for the years 2017–2020. This study uses the MAO as a proxy for FRQ. The results of this study confirmed that the characteristics of the chair of the audit committee have significant and clear impacts on the quality and efficiency of financial reports, which is in line with the findings of previous studies that have addressed this topic. The results also indicated that researchers, academics, regulators, and policymakers should not only look at the characteristics of audit committees as a whole, given that audit committee chairs affect financial reports. This study presents its contribution through an experimental demonstration of the characteristics of the chair of the audit committee and how these characteristics affect companies' financial reports. It also provides a guide for benefits for working to provide a basis for organizational procedures, especially those related to the impact on corporate boards and internal and external auditing.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

The principal and agent theory emerged in the 1970s from the combined disciplines of economics and institutional theory. There is some contention as to who originated the theory, with theorists Stephen Ross and Barry Mitnick claiming its authorship. Ross is said to have originally described the dilemma in terms of a person choosing a flavor of ice-cream for someone whose tastes he does not know. However, the most cited reference to the theory comes from Michael Jensen and William Meckling. The theory extends well beyond economics or institutional studies to all information asymmetry, uncertainty, and risk contexts.

The agency relationship is also viewed as a contractual process whereby owners delegate some of their authority and responsibilities to a team consisting of expert member(s), and they expect this team to exercise their expertise in the best interests of the company's operational success. Muth and Donaldson (2012) described the agency relationship as the delegation of power by the owner to the management. Eisenhardt (2013) discussed two major causes of agency problems: conflict of interests and different attitudes toward risk between the owner and management. In line with agency theory, the main problem of corporate governance is how shareholders ensure that self-seeking executives act in the shareholders' interests rather than their own (Hendry, 2012). When shareholders are unable to monitor management properly, the company's assets might be used for the welfare of management rather than maximizing the company's wealth (Al-Faryan, 2024; Berge and Means, 2012).

This study adopts agency theory because of its relevance in resolving conflicts that may arise between managers (agent) and shareholders (principal) of companies. In highlighting the importance of agency theory in CG, Christopher (2009) noted that the main concern of CG started from the separation of ownership and control in modern public corporations. In addition, Iman and Malik (2012), as cited in Eneh et al. (2024), noted that the

need for corporate governance arises from the potential for agency conflict. The main agency problem is between the controlling owner-management and outside shareholders. Jensen and Meckling (2014) described an agency relationship as “a contract under which one person (the principal) engages another person (the agent) to perform some services on his/her (the principal’s) behalf.”

Methodology

The research design for this study was an expo-facto research design. Expo-facto design involves describing the relationship between past factors and the present trend or occurrence. The study population included all 14 DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2024. Using the convenience sampling technique, the sample size of this study is made up of 13 listed DMBs that have been consistently listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and have published their financial report for the period under review, which are Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Jaiz bank, Stanbic IBTC Bank, Sterling Bank Plc, UBA Plc, Unity Bank Plc, Union Bank, Wema Bank Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc. However, Ecobank was listed as an incorporated Eco Transnational, and the data were quoted in dollars.

This study used a secondary method of data collection. The panel data were extracted from the published annual reports of listed DMBs in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. This study employed multiple regression analysis to identify, explain, and estimate the key relationship between corporate governance (audit committee composition, ownership concentration, and managerial ownership) and bank performance of listed DMBs in Nigeria. Panel data were analyzed using E-views version 12. Descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and regression analysis were performed, and post-estimation analyses, such as serial correlation and Hausman test, were also performed. The specific model given below for the Hausman test describes a convenient version for regression applications that involves testing whether certain transformations of the original regressors have zero coefficients.

The Model Specification:

The model adopted for this study is given as follows:

$$EPS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACC_{it} + \beta_2 OWC_{it} + \beta_3 MAO_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where;

EPS = earnings per share

ACC = Audit committee composition

OWC = ownership concentration

MAO = managerial ownership

β_0 = Constant

ε = Error term

$\beta_1, \beta_4,$ = the slope or coefficient of the independent variables.

Decision Rules

The decision rule to test the hypothesis of the study is as follows: The null hypothesis is rejected if the p-value of the t-coefficient is less than 5% (0.05).

Variable Measurement

Variable	Expected Sign	Measurement of the variables
Dependent Variable		
Financial Performance (Earnings per share)		Earnings per share (EPS) is calculated as Net Income-Preferred Dividends/Weighted Average Shares Outstanding.
Independent Variables		
Ownership concentration	Positive (+)	Measured by the percentage of large-block shareholders (Erin et al., 2021).
Composition of the Audit Committee	Positive (+)	The ratio of audit committee expertise to total audit committee size of a company is measured (Adebgoye et al., 2020).
Managerial Ownership	Positive (+)	Ratio of the number of shareholders divided by the total number of board members (Issa et al., 2021)

Results and Discussions**Table 2: Descriptive statistics**

	EPS	ACC	OWC	MAO
Mean	2.739978	0.751395	24.25172	0.637946
Median	1.449560	0.778151	20.00000	0.088693
Maximum	21.56036	0.903090	84.00000	9.287941
Minimum	-1.276200	0.477121	0.000000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	3.782942	0.075645	20.53881	1.734228
Skewness	2.782709	-1.870272	0.995664	3.655403
Kurtosis	12.35369	7.913925	3.214821	16.22426
Jarque-Bera	631.8159	203.4044	21.39485	1217.754
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000023	0.000000
Sum	350.7172	96.17858	3104.220	81.65715
Sum Sq. Dev.	1817.453	0.726707	53574.01	381.9585
Observations	128	128	128	128

Source: E-Views 12, 2025

The descriptive statistics show that EPS has a mean value of 2.74, indicating that, on average, listed DMBs generated modest earnings for shareholders over the study period. However, the wide range between the maximum (21.56) and minimum (1.28) profitability implies substantial variation across banks and periods. The high standard deviation (3.78) and strong positive skewness (2.78) imply that the distribution is pulled to the right by a few highly profitable banks. The kurtosis value (12.35) indicates a highly peaked distribution with fat tails, confirming the presence of extreme EPS values. The Jarque–Bera statistic is significant at 1%, indicating that the EPS is not normally distributed.

The mean value of 0.75 and relatively low standard deviation (0.08) for audit committee composition indicate limited variation across listed banks, suggesting that audit committee structures are fairly uniform likely due to regulatory requirements in Nigeria. However, the skewness (1.87) indicates a negatively skewed distribution, implying that the majority of banks have higher committee representation values, with fewer banks at the lower

end. The high kurtosis (7.91) and significant Jarque–Bera statistic show that the distribution deviates from normality, again likely reflecting a regulatory-driven clustering around similar committee sizes.

The results for ownership concentration show a mean of 24.25%, proposing that, on average, major shareholders hold approximately one-quarter of total bank shares, indicating moderate concentration among dominant investors. The large difference between the minimum (0%) and maximum (84%) and the high standard deviation (20.54) reveal substantial differences in ownership structures across Nigerian DMBs. The skewness (0.99) suggests a right-skewed distribution, indicating that a few banks have a very high concentration of ownership. Kurtosis (3.21) is close to that of a normal distribution, but the significant Jarque–Bera value indicates mild non-normality.

Managerial ownership exhibits a mean of 0.64%, indicating that managers generally hold very low equity stakes in Nigerian DMBs. The large gap between the maximum (9.29%) and minimum (0%) and the high standard deviation (1.73) signify that managerial ownership varies widely but remains low overall, consistent with the structure of large, publicly traded banks. The skewness (3.66) implies that most banks have near-zero managerial ownership, with only a few having relatively higher ownership levels. Extremely high kurtosis (16.22) and significant Jarque–Bera statistic demonstrate a highly non-normal distribution dominated by extreme values.

Table 3: Correlation matrix

	EPS	ACC	OWC	MAO
EPS	1	-0.1063	-0.0436	-0.0421
ACC	-0.1063	1	0.0776	0.0994
OWC	-0.0436	0.0776	1	-0.1173
MAO	-0.0421	0.0994	-0.1173	1

Source: E-Views 12, 2025

The correlation results show that EPS has a weak and negative relationship with all corporate governance variables. EPS was negatively correlated with audit committee composition ($r = 0.106$), ownership concentration ($r = 0.044$), and managerial ownership ($r = 0.042$). These coefficients are very close to zero, indicating that governance variables have only marginal linear associations with bank performance. In essence, changes in committee size, shareholder concentration, or managerial shareholding do not have a strong direct relationship with profitability. This indicates that board-level governance attributes may not directly influence earnings performance in a linear form for Nigerian DMBs or that the relationship may manifest more strongly through lagged or nonlinear channels.

The correlation between audit committee composition and ownership concentration is slightly positive ($r = 0.078$), although still very weak, suggesting that banks with slightly larger or more structured audit committees tend to have marginally higher ownership concentration. Similarly, audit committee composition has a weak positive relationship with managerial ownership ($r = 0.099$), indicating that improvements in committee structure do not deter managerial shareholding, but the association is too weak to be economically significant.

Ownership concentration shows a weak negative correlation with managerial ownership ($r = 0.117$), implying that highly concentrated ownership tends to have lower managerial shareholding. This is theoretically consistent with the idea that dominant shareholders often limit managers' ability to acquire substantial equity stakes, thereby reducing managerial control and potential agency conflicts.

The correlation results indicate the absence of multicollinearity, as all coefficients fall well below the critical threshold of 0.70. This implies that the variables can be used in regression analysis without the risk of distorted parameter estimates. The weak relationships also highlight that Nigerian DMBs' corporate governance

mechanisms may influence financial performance through more complex pathways not captured by simple pairwise correlations.

Table 3: Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq.		
	Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	3.635701	3	0.3036

Source: E-Views 12, 2025

The Hausman test compares the fixed- and random-effects estimators to determine which model is more appropriate for your panel data analysis. In your results, the chi-square statistic is 3.64 with 3 degrees of freedom, and the corresponding probability value is 0.3036. Since the p-value is greater than the conventional significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10%, the null hypothesis that the preferred model is the random effects estimator is not rejected.

This outcome implies that the differences between the fixed- and random-effects coefficients are not statistically significant. Therefore, the random-effects model is more consistent and efficient for estimating the relationship between the variables of corporate governance (audit committee composition, ownership concentration, and managerial ownership) and the earnings per share of listed DMBs. The random-effects model suggests that the variation across banks is largely random and not systematically tied to their corporate governance structures. Hence, the random-effects model provides more generalizable and efficient estimates for understanding CGD across Nigerian DMBs during the study period.

Table 4: Random-effect results

Dependent variable: Earnings_per_share

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects) analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ACC	10.70284	3.611070	2.963897	0.0036
OWC	-0.006907	0.025643	-0.269376	0.7881
MAO	0.512831	0.210138	2.440444	0.0161
C	11.21919	2.893021	3.878018	0.0002
Root MSE	2.721419	R-squared		0.103829
Mean var dependent	0.808680	Adjusted R-squared		0.082147
S.D.-dependent var	2.884540	S.E. of the regression		2.764965
Sum squared resid	947.9836	F-statistic		4.788793
Durbin-Watson stat	1.818714	Prob(F-statistic)		0.003427

Source: E-Views 12, 2025

The random effects regression model examines the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial performance of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks (DMBs) as measured by earnings per share (EPS). Overall, the model is statistically significant, with an F-statistic of 4.79 and a p-value of 0.0034, indicating that the governance variables jointly explain variations in EPS across the banks.

The composition of the audit committee has a significant positive effect on EPS, with a coefficient of 10.70 ($p = 0.0036$). Banks with better-structured audit committees, characterized by relevant expertise, stronger oversight, or optimal representation, tend to perform better financially. The result is consistent with corporate governance theory, which posits that effective monitoring mechanisms enhance transparency, reduce financial misreporting, and ultimately improve firm profitability.

Managerial ownership also has a significant positive influence on bank performance, with a coefficient of 0.513 ($p = 0.0161$). This implies that when managers hold a stake in the bank, their interests are better aligned with those of shareholders, leading to improved decision-making and profit-oriented strategies. This finding supports the argument of agency theory that managerial shareholding reduces agency conflicts and incentivizes performance-enhancing behavior.

However, ownership concentration has an insignificant effect on EPS ($\beta = -0.0069$, $p = 0.7881$), indicating that the proportion of shares held by major shareholders does not have a meaningful impact on profitability in Nigerian DMBs. This may reflect the regulatory environment in which dominant shareholders have limited influence on day-to-day operations, thus limiting their effect on financial outcomes.

In terms of model diagnostics, the R-squared value of 0.1038 indicates that the corporate governance variables explain approximately 10% of the variation in EPS, which is reasonable for firm-level studies where performance is influenced by numerous factors beyond governance. The random effects structure shows that 51% of the variation in EPS arises across banks, while 49% is due to within-bank variation over time. The results indicate that effective audit committee structures and managerial ownership significantly enhance financial performance, whereas ownership concentration does not exert a significant influence.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and the financial performance of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks (DMBs). The analysis indicates that audit committee composition has a positive and significant impact on EPS, suggesting that banks with well-structured audit committees experience enhanced profitability. This outcome aligns with agency theory, which emphasizes that effective monitoring mechanisms reduce agency conflicts between managers and shareholders, improve financial reporting quality, and foster investor confidence. The result is also consistent with the findings of Adegbite (2021) and Nduka et al. (2022), who found that the presence of competent audit committees strengthens oversight, reduces financial irregularities, and enhances firm performance in the Nigerian banking sector.

Similarly, managerial ownership is positively and significantly associated with EPS, indicating that managers are incentivized to pursue profit-maximizing strategies and align their actions with shareholder interests when they hold equity stakes in their banks. This finding supports the alignment hypothesis of agency theory, which posits that managerial shareholding mitigates agency problems by promoting responsible decision-making and firm value creation. It also corroborates Okike's (2019) and Eze et al.'s (2020) research that documented the positive effects of managerial ownership on corporate performance in emerging markets, including Nigeria.

In contrast, ownership concentration exhibits a negative but statistically insignificant effect on EPS, implying that the shareholding of dominant investors does not significantly influence bank profitability. This suggests that

regulatory frameworks, strict corporate governance codes, and central authorities' oversight in the Nigerian banking context may limit the ability of large shareholders to influence operational decisions. Consequently, ownership concentration alone may not be sufficient to enhance financial performance. This observation echoes Uwuigbe and Fakile (2017), who noted that concentrated ownership does not necessarily translate into improved earnings or efficiency in highly regulated banking environments.

Therefore, while certain governance mechanisms, particularly audit committee effectiveness and managerial ownership, play a crucial role in enhancing financial performance, not all governance structures uniformly affect profitability. The study highlights that the quality and functionality of governance mechanisms are critical determinants of firm performance in the Nigerian banking sector, rather than mere presence or concentration of ownership. These findings provide empirical support for strengthening board oversight, encouraging MEP, and refining governance policies to promote sustainable bank performance.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examined the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial performance of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks (DMBs), with earnings per share (EPS) as the measure of performance. The findings reveal that audit committee composition and managerial ownership are significant determinants of bank profitability. Banks with well-structured audit committees and higher managerial shareholdings tend to exhibit better financial performance, highlighting the importance of effective monitoring and alignment of managers' interests with those of shareholders. In contrast, ownership concentration had no significant impact on profitability, suggesting that the mere concentration of shares in the hands of dominant investors does not necessarily improve bank performance in the Nigerian context. Overall, the study underscores that the quality and functionality of governance mechanisms, rather than their mere presence or ownership concentration, are crucial drivers of Nigeria's banking sector's financial performance.

The policy recommendations are as follows:

- i. DMBs should ensure that audit committees comprise members who are independent, skilled, and adequately trained. Emphasis should be placed on enhancing oversight functions, risk management, and compliance to improve transparency and profitability.
- ii. DMBs should also consider mechanisms that allow managers to hold meaningful equity stakes, thereby aligning their interests with those of shareholders. Such alignment can enhance decision-making, accountability, and performance.
- iii. While ownership concentration does not directly affect performance, CBN should continue to monitor the influence of large shareholders to ensure that dominant investors do not engage in practices that undermine the interests or operational efficiency of minority shareholders.

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